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Deliverable 1.1 Demonstration report on validated prototypes from the three case studies

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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Deliverable 1.1 is a demonstrator and aims to validate the prototypes of the P2Green pilot regions. Over the past three years, the three pilot regions have developed and implemented innovative technologies to produce safe, bio-based fertilisers from human excreta and wastewater for agricultural production.

The German pilot region encompasses two technologies for the separate treatment of urine and dry toilet contents from festivals, public toilets, allotment gardens and off-grid nature tourism destinations. At Vagtshoff in Ollsen, GE operates a thermophilic, container-based composting plant that processes faeces from dry toilets and converts it into compost. In Eberswalde, KWB has installed a container-based liquid human waste VN system, which is supplemented by a distiller, to produce certified Aurin® from urine.

The Swedish pilot region led by S360 collects urine from portable separating toilets and dries it into a pelletised fertiliser for barley cultivation. Key innovations include the Kissamaja unisex urinal and mobile drying units that operate using waste heat.

The Spanish pilot region transforms municipal wastewater into nutrient-optimised irrigation water through BioA's treatment system in La Axarquía. TROPS uses smart fertigation technology from AGL to apply the product to one hectare of avocado and mango fields, showcasing optimised fertigation.

To demonstrate the establishment and operation of the four treatment plants, P2Green designed 360° augmented reality tours that allow the exploration of the facilities similar to an on-site visit.

Clicking the link below will direct you to the tours' landing page. Further down the page, you will find one tour for each pilot region's facility. Clicking on the respective frame, you will be taken directly to the tour's starting point. From there, you can look around (click and hold the left mouse button and drag the mouse) and navigate through the facility by clicking in the desired direction. An aerial view of the facility is available at the top right to help you orient yourself. Along the way, you will find many numbered blue tags containing descriptions, pictures and videos about the innovations.

After approval of the deliverable the landing page of the 360° augmented reality tours will become public and enable remote visits for all interested parties.

<https://p2green.eu/discover-p2greens-pilot-regions-and-learn-how-nutrient-recovery-works-in-practice/>

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